

Heteroleptic Ruthenium Complexes With 6-(Ortho-Substituted Phenyl)- 2,2'-Bipyridine Derivatives

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Abstract

Coordination chemistry of 2,2'-bipyridine bearing an ortho-substituted phenyl group at the 6-position, i.e., 6-(o-X-phenyl)-2,2'-bipyridine (MeO-L: X = OMe; Me₂N-L: X = NMe₂) with [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] (tpy = 4'- (4-tolyl)-2,2';6',2''-terpyridine) was investigated. The reaction of MeO-L and [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] in the presence of N-methylmorpholine afforded demethylated, O-coordinated complex [Ru(O-L)(tpy)]⁺ (O-L: X = O) as well as the cyclometalated, C-coordinated complex [Ru(MeO-L)(tpy)]⁺. On the other hand, reaction of Me₂N-L and [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] in the presence of N-methylmorpholine afforded only N-coordinated complex [Ru(Me₂N-L)(tpy)]²⁺. The crystal structures, spectroscopic and redox properties were examined supplemented by DFT calculations. The spectroscopic and redox properties of RuN are more or less similar to those of [Ru(tpy)Cl₃]. On the other hand, the properties of RuC and RuO are mutually similar but significantly different from those of RuN. The anionic ligand in RuC and RuO raises the HOMO energy as compared to the neutral ligand in RuN, which is

manifested in negatively shifted redox potentials, particularly the oxidation potentials, and thus, the red shift in the visible absorption band. Relevance of these complexes to sensitizers for dye-sensitized solar cells is briefly discussed.

Keywords

Coordination chemistry, Cyclometalated complex, Dye-sensitized solar cell, Ruthenium

1. Introduction

One of the promising classes of dyes for dye-sensitized solar cells (DSSCs) is cyclometalated ruthenium complexes [1,2]. This class of compounds have advantages with regard to durability over conventional polypyridine complexes bearing monodentate donor ligands such as isothiocyanate, which are prone to substitution under photovoltaic operation [3,4]. Also to the advantage of cyclometalated ligand, the introduction of substituents to the cyclometalated ligands is possible for tuning redox as well as spectroscopic properties of the complex, which is not the case for the isothiocyanate group. The Berlinguette group [1,2,5e7] and others [8,9] have developed a variety of cyclometalated complexes and revealed the factors that

affect the performance of DSSCs. As for the substitution effects on the phenyl group of 6-phenyl-2,2'-bipyridine, substituents at the 4, 5, and 6 positions have been

Fig. 1. Ruthenium complexes having an ambidentate 6-(o-substituted phenyl)-2,2'-bipyridine ligand.

ruthenium complex fragment, [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] (tpy = 4'-(4-methylphenyl)-2,2':6',2''-terpyridine). Heteroleptic complexes with the terpyridine ligand as an axillary ligand were chosen for investigation as these complexes may serve as model complexes for DSSCs. We found a reaction selectivity different from those described in the previous report and an interesting demethylation reaction. The selectivity of the reactions, the crystal structures of the complexes obtained, and physical properties of these complexes are described.

2. Experimental

2.1 General remarks

¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a JOEL JNM-ECX400 spectrometer. The numbering schemes for the assignment of ¹H NMR signals are presented in Fig. 2. ESI-HRMS were recorded on an Agilent LC/MSD TOF 1100 spectrometer. Me₂N-L [11], MeO-L [12], tpy [13], and [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] [14] were prepared

according to published procedures. Silica gel, Silica Gel 60 (spherical, 40e50 mm), for purification was purchased from Kanto Chemical. Spectroscopic grade CH₃CN for cyclic voltammetry and electronic absorption spectra was purchased from Kanto Chemical. Electronic absorption spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-2400PC. Cyclic voltammetry was performed using a Hokuto Denko HZ-3000 analyzer. Sample solution (0.1 mM) in CH₃CN containing 0.1 M NBu₄PF₆ was electrolyzed using Pt wires as the working and counter electrodes and Ag wire as the pseudo-reference electrode. The potentials were calibrated by internal ferrocene (Fc) added after each measurement and were converted to those with respect to the NHE, using the relations: 0 V vs. Fc⁺/Fc = +0.40 V vs. SCE (CH₃CN, NBu₄PF₆) [15] and 0 V vs. SCE = +0.24 V vs. NHE. Redox potentials in this report refer to values with respect to the NHE. DFT calculations were performed using Gaussian03, interfaced with GaussView. The single crystal diffraction analysis data were collected at 93 K with a Rigaku Saturn724+ diffractometer, a Rigaku R-Axis Rapid diffractometer, and a VariMax DW with Saturn diffractometer, respectively, for RuN, RuC, and RuO, using Mo K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71075 \text{ \AA}$)

The structures were solved by direct methods [16,17] and refined by full matrix least-squares calculations using SHELXL-97 [18].

2.2 Synthesis

2.2.1 General procedure

An ethylene glycol solution of the ligand (Me₂N-L or MeO-L), [Ru(tpy)Cl₃], and N-methylmorpholine was refluxed under Ar for 40 min. After the reaction was allowed to cool to room temperature, a saturated aqueous solution of NBu₄PF₆ was added, yielding precipitate. The precipitate was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, MeCN/0.4 M KNO₃ aq = 30/1). The solvent was mildly evaporated from the fraction collected to leave an aqueous solution, to which a saturated aqueous solution of NBu₄PF₆ was added. The resulting precipitate was collected and dried under vacuum.

222 [Ru(Me₂N-L)(tpy)][PF₆]₂ (RuN)

Me₂N-L (36 mg, 0.13 mmol), [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] (71 mg, 0.13 mmol), ethylene glycol (20 mL), and N-methylmorpholine (0.3 mL) were used to afford a brown solid. (48 mg, 0.058 mmol, 43%). TLC (silica gel, MeCN/0.4 M KNO₃ aq = 10/1): R_f = 0.4. ¹H NMR (CD₃CN): δ (ppm) = 2.20 (6H, s, NCH₃), 2.52 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.76 (1H, d,

J = 7.8 Hz, C₆), 6.99 (1H, dt, J = 6.9 Hz, A₅), 7.07 (1H, dd, J = 6.9 Hz, A₆), 7.06e7.21

(4H, br, D₅, D₆), 7.30 (1H, dt, J = 7.8 Hz, C₅), 7.47 (1H, dt, J = 7.8 Hz, C₄), 7.56 (2H, d, J = 7.9 Hz, F₃), 7.75 (1H, dt, J = 6.9 Hz, A₄), 7.91 (1H, dd, J = 7.8 Hz, C₃), 7.94 (2H, t, J = 8.0 Hz, D₄), 8.05 (2H, d, J = 7.9 Hz, F₂), 8.31 (1H, d, J = 6.9 Hz, A₃), 8.45 (1H, t, J = 8.1 Hz, B₄), 8.51 (1H, dd, J = 8.1 Hz, B₅), 8.58 (2H, d, J = 8.0 Hz, D₃), 8.60 (1H, dd, J = 8.1 Hz, B₃), 8.89 (2H, s, E₃). ESI-HRMS (CD₃CN): m/z calcd for C₄₀H₃₄F₆N₆PRu ([M]⁺), 845.1530; found, 845.1532. Analysis: calcd for C₄₀H₃₄F₁₂N₆P₂Ru \cdot CH₃CN, C 48.94, H 3.62, N 9.51%; found, C 48.73, H 3.61, N 9.25%.

223 [Ru(MeO-L)(tpy)][PF₆] (RuC) and [Ru(O-L)(tpy)][PF₆] (RuO)

MeO-L (101 mg, 0.38 mmol), [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] (204 mg, 0.39 mmol), ethylene glycol (40 mL), and N-methylmorpholine (0.5 mL) were used to afford both RuC (a purple solid, 71 mg, 0.085 mmol, 22%) and RuO (a dark red solid, 28 mg, 0.035 mmol, 9%).

Data for RuC. TLC (silica gel, MeCN/0.4 M KNO₃ aq = 10/1): R_f = 0.5. ¹H NMR (CD₃CN): δ (ppm) = 2.50 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.90 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.36 (1H, dd, J = 7.3 Hz, C₆), 6.35 (1H, dd, J = 7.3 Hz, C₄), 6.49 (1H, t, J = 7.3 Hz, C₅), 7.03e7.08 (3H, m, A₅, D₅), 7.42 (2H, td, J = 7.9 Hz, F₃), 7.44 (1H, td, J = 8.1 Hz, A₆), 7.52 (2H, d, J = 7.8 Hz, D₆), 7.77 (2H, dt, J = 7.8 Hz, D₄), 7.83 (1H, dt, J = 8.1 Hz, A₄), 8.04 (1H, t, J = 8.2 Hz, B₄), 8.06 (2H, d, J = 7.9 Hz, F₂), 8.36 (1H, dd, J = 8.2 Hz, B₃), 8.42 (1H, d, J = 8.1 Hz, A₃), 8.54 (2H, td, J = 7.8 Hz, D₃), 8.86 (2H, s, E₃), 8.91 (1H, dd, J = 8.2 Hz, B₅). ESI-HRMS (CD₃CN): m/z calcd for C₃₉H₃₀N₅ORu

([M]⁺), 686.1494; found, 686.1546. Analysis: calcd for C₃₉H₃₀F₆N₅OPRu, C 56.39, H 3.64, N 8.43%; found, C 56.56, H 3.83, N 8.49%.

Data for RuO. TLC (silica gel, MeCN/0.4 M KNO₃ aq = 10/1): R_f = 0.4. ¹H NMR ((CD₃)₂CO): δ (ppm) = 2.49 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.41 (1H, dd, J = 8.7 Hz, C6), 6.54 (1H, dt, J = 8.7 Hz, C4), 6.90 (1H, dt, J = 8.7 Hz, C5), 7.10 (1H, dt, J = 7.3 Hz, A5), 7.25 (2H, dt, J = 7.8 Hz, D5), 7.45 (2H, td, J = 7.8 Hz, D6), 7.48 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, F3), 7.60 (1H, d, J = 7.3 Hz, A6), 7.78 (1H, dt, J = 7.3 Hz, A4), 7.92 (2H, dt, J = 7.8 Hz, D4), 8.04 (1H, dd, J = 8.7 Hz, C3), 8.14 (2H, d, J = 8.2 Hz, F2), 8.44 (1H, t, J = 7.8 Hz, B4), 8.67 (1H, d, J = 7.3 Hz, A3), 8.67 (1H, d, J = 7.8 Hz, B5), 8.80 (2H, d, J = 7.8 Hz, D3), 8.81 (1H, dd, J = 7.8 Hz, B3), 9.05 (2H, s, E3). ESI-HRMS (CD₃CN): m/z calcd for C₃₈H₂₈N₅ORu ([M]⁺), 672.1337; found, 672.1386.

Analysis: calcd for C₃₈H₂₈F₆N₅OPRu·H₂O, C 54.68, H 3.62, N 8.39%; found, C 54.87, H 51, N 7.99%.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Reactions

A solution of the ligand (Me₂N-L or MeO-L), the complex fragment ([Ru(tppy)Cl₃]), and N-methylmorpholine in ethylene glycol was refluxed for 40 min (Scheme 1). Precipitate which resulted upon addition of Bu₄NPF₆ to the reaction mixture was purified through column chromatography to afford pure metal complexes. In the reaction of Me₂N-L and [Ru(tppy)Cl₃], N₆ type complex, RuN, was isolated after purification through column chromatography in 43% yield. The four resonances appear for the protons of the

anilino group, which indicates that the C-coordination was not involved but instead suggests that N-coordination occurred. The ESI-HRMS exhibited peaks around 845.1432 with z = +1, which corresponds to the mass of complex plus PF₆⁻. This result indicates that the charge of the complex is +2, in accord with the non-cyclometalated complex RuN (calcd for RuN·PF₆: m/z = 845.1530). The ESI-HRMS for the remaining materials in the reaction shows major peaks around m/z = 735.1614, in agreement with the mass and isotopic distribution of an incompletely substituted [Ru(tppy)(Me₂N-L)Cl]⁺

Scheme 1. Reaction of MeO-L or Me₂N-L and [Ru(tppy)Cl₃] in the presence of N-methylmorpholine.

Table 1 Crystallographic data.

	RuN	RuC	RuO
Formula	C ₄₄ H ₄₀ N ₈ Ru \$2(F ₆ P)	C ₃₉ H ₃₀ N ₅ O Ru\$F ₆ P	2(C ₃₈ H ₂₈ N ₅ OR u)\$2(F ₆ P ₂)\$C ₄ H ₁₀ O
Formula weight	1071.85	830.72	1707.50
Space group	<i>P</i> $\bar{1}$ (No. 2)	<i>P</i> 12/ <i>c</i> 1 (No. 13)	<i>P</i> 12/ <i>c</i> 1 (No. 13)
<i>a</i> / \AA	10.286(7)	18.1641(9)	18.323(9)
<i>b</i> / \AA	13.872(10)	8.8275(4)	9.434(4)
<i>c</i> / \AA	17.138(12)	23.3098(13)	21.434(10)
<i>a</i> ^o	66.802(13)	90.00	90.00
<i>b</i> ^o	77.16(2)	101.817(8)	110.281(7)
<i>g</i> ^o	78.92(2)	90.00	90.00
<i>V</i> / \AA^3	2176(3)	3658.4(4)	3475(3)
<i>Z</i>	2	4	2
<i>D</i> _{calc} /g cm ⁻³	1.635	1.508	1.632
<i>m</i> (Mo-K α)/mm ⁻¹	0.530	0.542	0.574
<i>T</i> /K	93	93	93
<i>R</i> [<i>F</i> ² > 2 <i>S</i> (<i>F</i> ²)]	0.054	0.097	0.084
<i>wR</i> (<i>F</i> ²)	0.145	0.254	0.199

(calcd: *m/z* = 735.1577) in which one of the chlorides remained; no cyclometalated complex was detected.

Ward et al. reported that reaction of Me₂N-L and RuCl₃ in a 2:1 ratio in the presence of N-methylmorpholine afforded the coordinatively heteroleptic complex, in which one of the ligands coordinated in a N₃ binding mode and the other in a N₂C mode, in addition to the homoleptic complex in which both ligands coordinated in a N₃ binding mode [11]. We carried out the reaction of Me₂N-L and [Ru(*ttpy*)Cl₃] in some other solvents (2-methoxyethanol, 1,2-dimethoxyethane, and methanol/water) in the presence of N-methylmorpholine but never obtained the cyclometalated complex.

On the other hand, the reaction of MeO-L and [Ru(*ttpy*)Cl₃] in the presence of N-methylmorpholine afforded cyclometalated, C-coordinated RuC as well as O-coordinated RuO. Under the

particular reaction conditions described in the Experimental section, the cyclometalated RuC was isolated in 22% yield and RuO was isolated in 9% yield. The main part of the remainder of the products was a pale yellow substance that sticks to the silica gel column and was unable to be characterized. Cyclometalation for RuC is indicated by a 1H NMR signal observed as a doublet at 5.36 ppm, an unusually upfield chemical shift for an aromatic proton, for the proton at the 6-position [19,20]. ESI-HRMS supports the cyclometalated structure by peaks with charge +1 including *m/z* = 686.1546 (calcd: *m/z* = 686.1494). Interestingly, we found that demethylation occurred in the process of forming the other complex, RuO. The largest set of MS peaks appear at around *m/z* = 672.1386 corresponding to the complex [Ru(O-L)(*ttpy*)]⁺ (calcd: *m/z* = 672.1337) with the anionic ligand produced by demethylation of MeO-L, which we denote as O-L. Further, the methyl signal is missing in the 1H NMR spectrum for RuO. A set of four signals (two doublets and two triplets) appear for the phenyl protons, excluding the possibility of a cyclometalated complex. The unequivocal evidence for the demethylation and O-coordination has come from the single-crystal X-ray analysis.

3.2 X-ray crystal structures

We have successfully grown single crystals of RuN, RuC, and RuO by the same protocol, that is, letting diethyl ether vapor diffuse into a solution of the complex in acetonitrile, and obtained X-ray structures of these complexes. The

crystallographic data are tabulated in Table 1, selected bond lengths and angles are presented in Table 2, and the structures are displayed in Fig. 3; full information on the crystallography is found in Supplementary material.

The crystal structure for RuN shows that the Me₂N-L ligand coordinates to the ruthenium in a N₃-type coordination. This tridentate coordination and the other tridentate coordination by the ttpy ligand afford an octahedral N₆ coordination. The bond length between the amine nitrogen and the ruthenium atom,

N(8)eRu, is 2.19 Å, the longest among the six Ru-N bond lengths; the other lengths range from 1.98 to 2.09 Å. The three C-N(8)-C angles in the dimethylamino substituent are 105.6°, 107.4°, and 113.2°, which are closer to the tetrahedral angle than to the triangular angle, which indicates that the nitrogen adopts the sp³ hybrid orbital [11]. Thus, there is no back-donation to the sp³ nitrogen, accounting for the long bond length. The two pyridine rings of Me₂N-L lie nearly planar with the dihedral angle of 7.6°, while the phenyl ring is significantly twisted with respect to the central pyridine plane by 42°. One of the pyridine rings in the ttpy ligand is also distorted out of the plane of the central pyridine ring by 12.6° apparently due to steric effects of the dimethylamino group in the counter ligand.

The crystal structure for RuC shows that the complex is indeed a cyclometalated complex with the C-Ru bond (bond length, 2.03 Å). The bond length between

the Ru and pyridine-N(4) trans to the coordinated C(33) is 2.14 Å. This is distinctly longer than those between the other peripheral pyridine-N's and Ru, which range from 2.02 to 2.06 Å. This elongation may suggest the trans influence of the coordinated carbon, although it is difficult to distinguish the

Selected bond lengths		angles (°)			
RuN		RuC		RuO	
Ru(1)eN(5)	2.048(5)	Ru(1)eN(4)	2.142(7)	Ru(1)eN(1)	2.036(6)
Ru(1)eN(7)	2.042(4)	Ru(1)eN(5)	2.018(6)	Ru(1)eN(2)	2.026(6)
Ru(1)eN(8)	2.188(5)	Ru(1)eC(33)	2.028(8)	Ru(1)eO(1)	2.040(5)
N(5)eRu(1)eN(8)	167.41(13)	N(4)eRu(1)eC(33)	157.1(3)	N(1)eRu(1)eO(1)	92.9(2)
N(7)eRu(1)eN(8)	88.68(17)	N(5)eRu(1)eC(33)	80.0(3)	N(2)eRu(1)eO(1)	172.0(2)
Ru(1)eN(8)eC(38)	107.7(3)			Ru(1)eO(1)eC(1)	122.6(4)

Table 2

Fig. 3. Crystal structures. Non-hydrogen atoms are drawn as ellipsoids at the 50% probability level and H atoms as spheres of arbitrary size. (a) RuN. (b) RuC. (c) RuO.

electronic effects from structural effects because the coordinated carbon and the trans nitrogen belong to the same ligand.

The crystal structure of RuO unequivocally demonstrates that the methyl group, which was present in the ligand MeO-L, has been lost upon complexation and the oxygen coordinates to the ruthenium with a formal charge of -1 . The length of the RuO bond is 2.04 Å, slightly longer than those previously observed in [Ru(O-L)₂] (1.95–1.97 Å) [10]. The dihedral angle between the phenyl ring and the central pyridine ring is 19°. The three pyridine rings in the counter ttpy ligand lie nearly planar in this case.

3.3 Electrochemistry and spectroscopy

The redox behaviors were probed by cyclic voltammetry as shown in Fig. 4 (see Supplementary materials for numerical data). The redox reactions were nearly reversible for the oxidations for all the complexes and the first reductions for RuN and RuC. The second reductions for RuN and RuC and the reductions for RuC and RuO exhibited quasireversible behaviors with peak separations wider than the diffusion-limited value by 10³ mV at the scan rate of 100 mV s⁻¹. The redox potentials in acetonitrile for RuN are +1.49 V vs. NHE for oxidation and -0.98 V and -1.31 V and for consecutive reductions, which are quite similar to those for [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ (+1.49 V, -1.00 V, and -1.24 V). On the other hand, the redox behaviors of RuC and RuO are mutually similar but different from those of RuN and [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺, being oxidized at +0.76 V and +0.69 V and reduced at -1.33 V and -1.20 V, respectively. The latter two complexes are thus easier to oxidize and harder to reduce. For these latter two complexes, the gap between the oxidation

potential and the first reduction potential are around 2.0 V, which are smaller than those for RuN and [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺, which are around 2.5 V. This is in agreement with the electronic absorption spectra, where the visible absorption maxima undergo red-shifts on going from [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ (490 nm) and RuN (496 nm) to RuC (520 nm) and RuO (537 nm), as shown in Fig. 5. The differences between the former two and the latter two can be qualitatively attributed to the formal charge of the coordinating atom. In the former two complexes, all of the coordinating atoms are the neutral nitrogen, whereas, in the latter two, one of the coordinating atoms are formally negative carbon or oxygen. Negative atoms are stronger σ donors than the neutral counterparts and push up the metal orbital levels, e.g., the HOMO level, which accounts for the negative shift in the redox potentials, particularly the oxidation potentials and the red-shift in the absorption spectra. Theoretical calculations were performed to reveal the electronic structures of these complexes more quantitatively.

3.4 Theoretical calculations

Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were performed using B3LYP/LanL2DZ on the crystal structures to supplement the experimental findings. The coordinates of [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ were taken from the crystal structure in the literature [17]. There are two nonequivalent molecules in the crystal, both of which we used for calculations. For the other complexes, the coordinates in the

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammetry in 1 mM sample solutions in CH₃CN containing 0.1 M NBu₄PF₆, with Pt, Pt, and Ag electrodes as the working, counter, and pseudo-reference electrodes (scan rate: 100 mV s⁻¹). The potentials were calibrated with internal ferrocene added after each measurement.

present study were used. Counter anions were not included in the calculations. The results on the HOMO and LUMO are summarized in Table 3. In addition to the molecular orbital energies and diagrams, the fractions of fragments in the molecules have been analyzed as shown in SI.

First thing to note for these complexes is the large difference in the HOMO energies. For [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ and RuN, the HOMO energies of are -10.4 and -10.6 eV, respectively. On the other hand, for RuC and RuO, they are -7.4 and -7.1 eV, respectively. The difference between the former two complexes and the latter two is obviously due to the difference in charge of the coordinating atoms; Ru in [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ and RuN is coordinated by neutral nitrogen ligands, while that in RuC

and RuO is coordinated by a negatively charged C or O ligand.

For [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺, the HOMO is rather evenly distributed between the metal and the ligands, while the LUMO is predominantly ligand-based (see Table S5). The frontier orbitals of RuN is similar to those of [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ in a sense that the HOMO is distributed over the metal and the tpy ligands and the LUMO is predominantly localized in the tpy ligand. The frontier orbitals of RuC and RuO are different from those of [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ and RuN but are mutually similar in a sense that the HOMO is a mixture of the (Me)O-L ligand-based and the metal-based, while the LUMO is predominantly the tpy ligand-based.

With the assignments of the molecular orbitals to the molecular fragments, the electrochemically obtained redox reactions can now be assigned to the molecular fragments. In the case of the oxidation of RuC and RuO, which occurs at lower potentials than the others, an electron is taken from the hybrid orbitals (which is the HOMO) of the Ru d orbitals and the anionic ligands, MeO-L and O-L, respectively. For [Ru(tpy)₂]²⁺ and RuN, which are oxidized at higher potentials, an electron is taken from the hybrid orbitals (which is the HOMO) of the Ru d orbitals and the tpy ligand. As for the reductions, the first reduction is tpy-based for all of these complexes, since the LUMO of all complexes are on the tpy ligand. Yet, the reduction potentials of RuC and RuO are more negative than the others by ca. 200e300 mV, which is indicative of the

strong electron-donating nature of the anionic ligands, MeO-L and O-L.

Time-dependent DFT (TD-DFT) calculations were performed using the same functional and the basis set (B3LYP/LanL2DZ) to obtain the lowest 20 electronic excited states of these complexes. The transition energies and the oscillator strengths are shown along with the experimental electronic spectra in Fig. 5. For $[\text{Ru}(\text{ttpy})_2]^{2+}$, the calculated transitions nicely reproduce the observed visible absorption spectrum. The major transitions with large oscillator strengths between 400 and 500 nm consist of HOMO / LUMO, HOMO / LUMO + 1, and HOMO - 2 / LUMO + 1 as the major components. For RuN, the visible absorption band around 500 nm consists of various transitions from occupied to unoccupied frontier orbitals ranging mainly from the HOMO - 2 to LUMO + 2. For RuC, the major calculated transition corresponding to the visible absorption band is found at 488 nm for the HOMO - 2 to LUMO + 1. This transition is from a hybrid orbital of the metal and MeO-L to an

Fig. 5. UV-vis absorption spectra in CH₃CN and transitions obtained by TD-DFT calculations (B3LYP/LANL2DZ). (a) and (b) $[\text{Ru}(\text{ttpy})_2]^{2+}$ [21]. Two nonequivalent molecules exist in the crystal. (c) RuN. (d) RuC. (e) RuO.

orbital localized on the ttpy ligand. Thus, the visible band for RuC is assigned as a combined band of metal-to-ttpy charge transfer and MeO-L-to-ttpy interligand charge transfer transitions. Other small-intensity transitions include various transitions between the HOMO - 2 and LUMO + 2. It is interesting to note that the HOMO to LUMO transition is not the major contributor to the transition.

For RuO, the large visible absorption band around 540 nm consists of various transitions from occupied to unoccupied frontier orbitals ranging mainly from the HOMO - 3 to LUMO + 4. In addition, a long wavelength tail is observed experimentally down to 800 nm. The presence of the long wavelength absorption is well reproduced by the TD-DFT calculations. Two transitions are found at 719 nm and 675 nm corresponding to HOMO to LUMO + 1 and HOMO to LUMO + 2 transitions, respectively. The HOMO is mainly localized on the phenoxy moiety in the O-L ligand while the LUMO + 1 and LUMO + 2 are localized on the bipyridine moiety in the O-L ligand and the ttpy ligand. Thus, these transitions have intraligand and interligand charge transfer characters.

Table 3

HOMOs and LUMOs according to B3LYP/LanL2DZ.

3.5 Perspectives for DSSCs

Finally, we will briefly discuss the energetics of these complexes in view of potential applications to DSSCs. The critical factors for the DSSC dyes are the LUMO level that is responsible for charge injection into the TiO₂ conduction band and the HOMO level that is responsible for the dye regeneration by the iodine redox couple, I^{-2•}/I⁻ (+0.79 V) [22]. To apply

the present complexes to DSSCs, the anchoring groups such as the carboxyl groups should be introduced. For example, the ttpy ligand may be replaced by 4,4',4''-tricarboxy-2,2':6',2''-terpyridine (tctpy) in this regard. With this replacement, the orbital levels are expected to change. We may estimate the degree of change in the HOMO and LUMO levels brought about by the ligand replacement by comparing reported values for complexes with a ttpy ligand and a tctpy ligand [23,24]. The energy levels of complexes bearing a tctpy ligand can be further tuned by adjusting the degree of proton dissociation of the carboxyl groups. It is estimated that the shifts of the HOMO and LUMO levels by replacing the ttpy ligand by the tctpy ligand are in a range of 0.1 eV and -0.4 to +0.15 eV, respectively.

Taking these expected shifts into consideration, the LUMO levels of the complexes in which ttpy is replaced by tctpy from the present complexes (denoted with a prime), RuN' (-0.6 V to -1.11 V), RuC' (-0.9 V to -1.5 V), and RuO' (-0.8 V to -1.3 V). Although the conduction band edge position varies significantly depending on the conditions of preparation of TiO₂ electrode, we may refer a typical value of -0.6 V vs. NHE [25,26]. It is thus most likely that the LUMO levels of the present complexes are high enough with significant margins for charge injection. The HOMO levels of the complexes in which the ttpy is replaced by tctpy are expected to be +1.6 V to +1.4 V for RuN', +0.9 V to +0.7 V for RuC', and +0.8 V to +0.6 V for RuO'. Thus, it is likely

that the HOMO level of the RuN' is low enough for effective regeneration; that of RuC' may be just low enough. On the other hand, the HOMO of RuO' may be somewhat too high.

4. Conclusion

Coordination chemistry of 6-(o-X-phenyl)-2,2'-bipyridine (MeO- L: X = OMe; Me2N-L: X = NMe2) with [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] (tpy = 4'-(4-tolyl)-2,2';6',2''-terpyridine) was investigated. The reaction of MeO- L and [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] in the presence of N-methylmorpholine afforded demethylated, O-coordinated complex [Ru(O-L)(tpy)]⁺ (RuO) as well as the cyclometalated, C-coordinated complex [Ru(MeO- L)(tpy)]⁺ (RuC). On the other hand, reaction of Me₂N-L and [Ru(tpy)Cl₃] in the presence of N-methylmorpholine afforded only N-coordinated complex [Ru(Me₂N-L)(tpy)]₂⁺ (RuN).

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